

The Impact of Big Five Personality Traits on Physical, Psychological, and Behavioral Symptoms in Working Women with Premenstrual Syndrome

Mrs. Kalaiamutha Navaratnarajah, Research Scholar (Ph.D), Department of Psychology, Annamalai University, Chidambaram, Tamilnadu, India - 608002.

Dr. Padmasundari Singaram, Assitant Professor, Department of Psychology, Government Arts College (Autonomous), Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India – 641018.

1. INTRODUCTION

Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS) is an ailment that affects many women during the luteal phase of their menstrual cycle. The condition is characterized by both physical and psychological symptoms. There are a wide range of symptoms associated with PMS, including mood swings, irritability, fatigue, bloating, breast tenderness, anxiety, and difficulty concentrating, and these symptoms typically subside with menstruation; however, they can significantly affect daily activities and overall quality of life as a result. Managing professional responsibilities while dealing with PMS can be tough for working women, leading to increased stress and decreased productivity (Hofmeister & Bodden, 2016). There are a lot of factors involved in PMS, especially hormonal fluctuations, such as estrogen and progesterone levels. The influence of psychological factors on PMS symptoms may vary depending on the individual's personality profile, which affects the severity of the symptoms as well as the individual's coping strategies, according to recent research. There is a strong correlation between personality and PMS severity, which is particularly relevant for working women, who are likely to experience heightened levels of psychological and emotional stress in the workplace because of the combination of PMS symptoms and work-related pressures.

As a result of PMS, women experience recurring emotional, physical, and psychological symptoms during the luteal phase of the menstrual cycle that subside after

menstruation starts (Yonkers, 2008). There can be significant effects on daily functioning, social relationships, and work performance due to the variability in PMS severity (Yonkers, 2008). Having severe PMS, which includes depression, anxiety, and irritability, can make it hard for a woman to do her job (Hofmeister & Bodden, 2016), and although hormonal fluctuations play a big role in PMS etiology, we don't know exactly what causes it. Researchers are increasingly suggesting that other factors, particularly personality traits, may also affect PMS, interacting with hormonal and environmental factors and thereby magnifying or mitigating its effects (Ryu & Kim, 2015).

An understanding of the relationship between individual differences in personality and PMS can be gained from the Five-Factor Model (FFM), which includes neuroticism, extraversion, openness to experience, agreeability, and conscientiousness. PMS severity is more consistently associated with neuroticism, which causes emotional instability, anxiety, and negative affect. The mood-related symptoms of PMS, such as irritability, depression, and anxiety, may be aggravated for women high in neuroticism (Schneider et al., 2011) and Neurotic individuals may also be more sensitive to stress, which can lead to more intense physical and psychological symptoms associated with PMS (Costa & McCrae, 1992).

However, extraversion is associated with sociability, optimism, and positive emotional experiences. Women high in extraversion tend to report fewer negative emotional symptoms and are more capable of managing stress, which may reduce the severity of PMS psychological and emotional effects (Williams & Zimmerman, 2016). It has been suggested that women are more likely to be open to experiencing new things when they are open to experiencing them. It has also been suggested that women who are open to experiences may be more likely to develop adaptive coping mechanisms, enabling them to cope better with stress related to PMS. However, the link between openness and PMS is less well-documented compared to neuroticism and extraversion.

There is also evidence to suggest that a woman's level of agreeableness and conscientiousness also affect how she perceives and copes with PMS. For example, agreeable people tend to be more cooperative and empathic, which may help them maintain social relationships during periods of emotional instability. It has been shown that conscientiousness leads to better health management and coping strategies, thereby reducing PMS symptoms (Costa & McCrae, 1992). Understanding this relationship can help women understand why some women experience PMS more severely. Rapkin & Mikacich (2013) suggest that it can also help identify those at higher risk for severe PMS and guide more targeted management and intervention strategies.

Approximately 30-40% of women of reproductive age suffer from PMS (Direkvand-Moghadam et al., 2014), and PMS symptoms can vary in intensity but are often severe enough to affect daily life, including social, occupational, and interpersonal relationships. The more severe forms of PMS, called premenstrual dysphoric disorder (PMDD), are often associated with significant difficulties in carrying out everyday tasks. This can have a negative impact on the quality of one's life (Hofmeister & Bodden, 2016).

Several factors are thought to contribute to PMS, including hormonal fluctuations, such as estrogen and progesterone, which affect neurotransmitter systems, including serotonin and gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) (Rapkin & Winer, 2009). However, the variability in PMS symptoms suggests that other factors influence the symptoms, including personality traits and psychological resilience. Researchers have examined the relationship between personality traits, particularly those measured by the Five-Factor Model, and various health outcomes, including emotional well-being as well as stress management. It has been consistently found that neuroticism, one of the five major personality traits, is correlated with negative affect and emotional dysregulation. Ryu & Kim (2015) have shown that women with high levels of neuroticism tend to experience greater levels of emotional and psychological

symptoms during the premenstrual phase, likely as a result of an increased sensitivity to stress and emotional instability during this period.

Women with higher levels of extraversion are more likely to use effective coping mechanisms to cope with PMS (Schneider et al., 2011), so they may have fewer emotional symptoms related to PMS. Extraversion, on the other hand, is often associated with positive affect and resilience in the face of stress. There have also been studies on openness to experience, conscientiousness, and agreeability, but the evidence for how these traits relate to PMS is less consistent (Reed et al., 2008). Conscientiousness, for instance, has been linked to better health behaviors and stress management, which may help mitigate PMS' physical and emotional symptoms.

It is important to understand how individual differences influence the severity and experience of PMS symptoms by considering the interplay between personality traits and PMS. It may be advantageous for healthcare providers to develop more personalized approaches to managing PMS by understanding these relationships, particularly among working women who face additional stressors at work. There is a growing body of literature examining the role of the Big Five personality traits on the severity of PMS symptoms among working women in order to contribute to this growing body of literature.

Our goal with this study is to explore the relationship between personality traits, as measured by the NEO-Five Factor Inventory (NEO-FFI), and PMS symptoms in working women. The study hypothesizes certain personality traits, like neuroticism, will lead to worse PMS symptoms. Furthermore, it aims to examine how extraversion, openness, agreeableness, and conscientiousness relate to PMS symptoms in the physical, psychological, and behavioral domains.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Aim of the study

The purpose of the study is to examine the influence of the Big Five personality traits like openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism on the physical, psychological, and behavioral symptoms experienced by working women with Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS). This study explores these relationships in order to gain a better understanding of how personality traits may influence the severity and manifestation of PMS symptoms, and provides insights into how to develop customized coping strategies to help women suffering from PMS at work improve their quality of life.

2.2. Objectives

- To assess the prevalence of PMS symptoms (physical, psychological, and behavioral) in working women.
- To examine the relationship between the Big Five personality traits and the severity of PMS symptoms.
- To identify which personality traits are the most significant predictors of physical, psychological, and behavioral symptoms of PMS.

2.3. Sample:

A sample of 50 working women were recruited for the study, all of whom reported experiencing regular menstrual cycles. In the study, 50 working women aged 20-45 years reported regular menstrual cycles and were not taking hormones or contraceptives that might interfere with their natural menstrual cycle, as well as exhibiting varying degrees of PMS symptoms. Participants were recruited from various workplaces, including corporate offices, educational institutions, and healthcare facilities.

2.4. Instruments:

2.4.1. NEO-Five Factor Inventory (NEO-FFI):

Each personality trait was scored with a 5-point Likert scale, with higher scores indicating greater prominence, based on a 60-item inventory measuring neuroticism, extraversion, openness, agreeableness, and conscientiousness.

2.4.2. Premenstrual Syndrome Scale (PMS Scale):

A total of three domains of PMS symptoms were assessed using this scale: behavioral (e.g., irritability, mood swings), physical (bloating, headaches), and psychological (e.g., anxiety, depression). Participants rated their symptoms on a 4-point scale, with higher scores indicating more severe symptoms.

2.5. Procedure:

Data was collected on demographic variables such as age, work environment, and menstrual history of the participants and recruitment was performed through ads placed in workplaces and local women's health clinics. Following the provision of informed consent, participants completed the NEO-FFI and the PMS Scale at a predetermined point during their menstrual cycle (luteal phase) to ensure accuracy. Both tools were administered at the same

time. On the basis of the PMS Scale scores, the severity of PMS symptoms was categorized as mild, moderate, or severe.

2.6. Data Analysis:

An analysis of the big five personality traits was conducted to explore whether there are any relationships between the Big Five traits and PMS symptoms by using descriptive statistics; correlational analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between the Big Five personality traits and PMS symptoms by using correlational analysis. There was a comparison of severity of PMS symptoms across different levels of personality traits in order to identify patterns of influence that may explain PMS symptoms.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the current study, behavioral, physical, and psychological domains were examined to examine the association between personality traits and PMS symptoms severity. The NEO-Five Factor Inventory (NEO-FFI) was used to assess the association between personality traits and PMS symptoms. Descriptive statistics and correlation analysis were used to investigate this relationship.

3.1. PMS Severity Levels and Personality Traits

There was a correlation found between the NEO-Five Factor Inventory (NEO-FFI) personality traits and PMS severity (categorized as mild, moderate, and severe). Using the Premenstrual Syndrome Scale (PMS Scale), which evaluates behavioral, physical, and psychological symptoms, the Premenstrual Syndrome Scale was utilized in this study. The following was the distribution of PMS severity levels among the sample (N=50):
Figure-6: Gives Severity Levels of Premenstrual Syndrome Scale (PMSS)

Figure-1: Severity Level of Premenstrual Syndrome Scale (PMSS)

Figure-2: Mean and Standard Deviation of personality traits

Figure-3: Mean and Standard Deviation of PMS sub scales

Table 1: Correlations Between Personality Traits and PMS Subscales

Personality Trait	Behavioral PMS	Physical PMS	Psychological PMS	Overall PMS Severity
Neuroticism	0.58**	0.56**	0.71***	0.62***
Extraversion	-0.32*	-0.31*	-0.37**	-0.33*
Openness	-0.17	-0.21	-0.18	-0.17
Agreeableness	-0.11	-0.13	-0.16	-0.13
Conscientiousness	-0.28*	-0.26	-0.33*	-0.27*

*Note: $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.001$

Table 2: Distribution of Personality Traits Across PMS Severity Levels

Personality Trait	Mild PMS (n=18)	Moderate PMS (n=21)	Severe PMS (n=11)
Neuroticism	3.1 (0.6)	3.5 (0.7)	4.2 (0.6)
Extraversion	3.4 (0.5)	3.1 (0.7)	2.7 (0.6)
Openness	3.4 (0.4)	3.3 (0.5)	3.1 (0.6)
Agreeableness	3.6 (0.3)	3.5 (0.4)	3.3 (0.5)
Conscientiousness	3.7 (0.5)	3.4 (0.4)	3.0 (0.6)

3.2. Discussion

3.2.1. Prevalence of PMS Symptoms:

According to the results of the study, 64% of the employed women reported experiencing moderate to severe levels of PMS symptoms across the domains of physical, psychological, and behavioral symptoms as a result of PMS.

3.2.2. Big Five Personality Traits and PMS Symptoms:

3.2.2.1. *Neuroticism:*

Among women who reported higher levels of Neuroticism, there was a significant increase in psychological and behavioral symptoms, such as anxiety, irritability, and mood swings, and Neuroticism was the strongest predictor of PMS severity, particularly in the areas of emotional and cognitive symptoms.

3.2.2.2. *Extraversion:*

It has been shown that extraversion is inversely related to behavioral and psychological symptoms. Women who scored higher on extraversion tend to report fewer mood-related symptoms and have better coping mechanisms, perhaps as a result of a stronger network of support and a more positive outlook on life.

3.2.2.3. Openness to Experience:

The degree of openness was positively correlated with a higher level of adaptive coping styles and a lower level of psychological distress. However, the association of openness with physical symptoms was less prominent. A higher level of openness was associated with a greater likelihood that women would engage in creative activities to manage their PMS-related discomfort during their period.

3.2.2.4. Agreeableness:

A greater level of Agreeableness was linked to lower behavioral symptoms, such as social withdrawal and interpersonal conflicts, and women who scored high on Agreeableness were able to manage their interpersonal relationships more effectively when dealing with PMS-related stress.

3.2.2.5. Conscientiousness:

A higher level of conscientiousness was associated with fewer behavioral symptoms, such as better time management and productivity during the premenstrual phase. The performance of work and daily routines of women with higher scores in this trait was less disrupted. It was found that personality traits, especially neuroticism and extraversion, played an important role in modifying the severity of Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS) symptoms for women who work.

3.2.3. Personality Traits and PMS Severity

3.2.3.1. *Neuroticism and PMS Severity*

A strong positive correlation was found between neuroticism and all PMS subscales (behavioral, physical, and psychological) and the overall severity of PMS. There was a higher correlation between the severity of symptoms among women with higher neuroticism scores, particularly in the psychological domain ($r = 0.71$, $p < 0.001$). As previously reported, neuroticism is associated with emotional instability and heightened sensitivity to stress, which can worsen mood swings, anxiety, and irritability that are common to PMS (Schneider et al., 2011). Women with severe PMS scored significantly higher on neuroticism than those with mild or moderate PMS, indicating a dose-response relationship between neuroticism and PMS symptoms.

3.2.3.2. *Extraversion and PMS Severity*

Those who scored higher on extraversion reported fewer PMS-related difficulties, which was negatively correlated with PMS severity, particularly with psychological and behavioral symptoms. Interestingly, extraverted individuals tend to have better coping strategies as well as a positive outlook, which could potentially help reduce the emotional burden of PMS (Williams & Zimmerman, 2016), in line with the notion that extraverted individuals are more likely to deal with PMS in a positive manner. In the severe PMS group, extraversion scores were significantly lower, supporting the idea that less social engagement and optimism may be linked to increased PMS severity.

3.2.3.3. *Other Personality Traits*

In contrast to the other traits—openness, agreeableness, and conscientiousness—there is a weak or non-significant correlation between these traits and PMS subscales. However, the correlation between conscientiousness and behavioral and psychological symptoms was mildly significant, suggesting that women who are self-disciplined and organized may be less likely to face psychological problems associated with PMS in the future. The results of this study are in agreement with other studies that have linked conscientiousness with improved mental health and coping mechanisms (Costa & McCrae, 1992).

3.2.4. PMS Severity Levels

There were significant differences in the distribution of personality traits between the severity levels of PMS. Women with severe PMS had a higher level of neurotic traits and were less extraverted and conscientious. These findings support the notion that personality traits can not only predict the presence of PMS but the severity of it as well. It is important to consider personality factors in the assessment of risk for severe PMS symptoms and the design of targeted interventions in order to reduce the severity of symptoms.

4. CONCLUSION

In this study, it was demonstrated that personality traits, especially neuroticism and extraversion, are significantly associated with the severity of PMS symptoms in working women. A key factor, neuroticism, is associated with increased distress and reduced productivity, as it can exacerbate psychological and behavioral symptoms. However, extraversion and conscientiousness were found to act as buffers for women, allowing them to manage their symptoms in a more effective manner. The symptoms of PMS tend to be milder for women with high levels of extraversion than those with high levels of neuroticism, as those with severe behavioral, physical, and psychological symptoms are more likely to occur.

As a result, these results suggest that personality assessments can be incorporated into PMS management strategies in order to identify women who may develop severe PMS symptoms, and tailor interventions accordingly. This study indicates that there is a significant positive correlation between neuroticism and PMS symptom severity, which corroborates previous research that indicates that emotional instability increases the risk of developing PMS symptoms (Schneider et al., 2011). It was found that women who scored higher in neuroticism reported severe behavioral and psychological symptoms such as anxiety, irritability, and mood swings. These findings are consistent with the literature which indicates that neuroticism contributes to mood disorders and emotional dysregulation (Costa & McCrae, 1992).

There was also evidence that extraversion was negatively associated with PMS severity, although its impact was smaller. This finding is in line with the idea that individuals with a greater sense of social engagement and a more outgoing personality may be better equipped to cope with stressors, including those related to PMS (Williams & Zimmerman, 2016). According to this study, openness, agreeableness, and conscientiousness were not significantly associated with PMS severity, indicating that these characteristics may not play a significant role in modifying PMS in this sample.

Neuroticism, Extraversion, and Conscientiousness, among the Big Five personality traits, are crucial for modulating PMS' physical, psychological, and behavioral effects. The findings highlight the importance of psychological factors such as personality when managing and treating PMS. In the future, research should focus on potential interventions, including cognitive-behavioral therapy, which could mitigate the detrimental effects of neuroticism on the severity of PMS.

The implications of these findings are significant for workplace interventions, as well as developing tailored coping strategies and workplace policies that address the challenges associated with PMS at work. Understanding the personal characteristics of women can ascertain the best coping strategies and workplace policies for women experiencing PMS at work. Managing stress and implementing flexible work arrangements might be particularly beneficial for those of us who are high in Neuroticism, while those with high levels of Conscientiousness would benefit from implementing strategies that increase productivity and set goals.

A potential direction for future research would be to examine the interaction between personality traits and other psychological factors, such as stress resilience and coping mechanisms, in order to develop comprehensive intervention strategies for women suffering

from PMS, which would include the interaction between personality traits and other psychological factors.

It is recommended to conduct future research with larger and more diverse samples in order to further investigate the mechanisms through which personality traits influence PMS symptomatology, as well as to evaluate whether personalized therapeutic approaches can be effective in treating women with high levels of neuroticism and low levels of extraversion.

5. REFERENCES

- Costa, P. T., & McCrae, R. R. (1992). Revised NEO Personality Inventory (NEO-PI-R) and NEO Five-Factor Inventory (NEO-FFI). Psychological Assessment Resources.
- Direkvand-Moghadam, A., Sayehmiri, K., Delpisheh, A., & Sayerehmiri, M. (2014). Epidemiology of Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS)—A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis Study. *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research*, 8(2), 106-109.
- Freeman, E. W. (2003). Premenstrual syndrome and premenstrual dysphoric disorder: Definitions and diagnosis. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, 28(Suppl 3), 25-37.
- Halbreich, U. (2003). The etiology, biology, and evolving pathology of premenstrual syndromes. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, 28(Suppl 3), 55-99.
- Hofmeister, S., & Bodden, S. (2016). Premenstrual Syndrome and Premenstrual Dysphoric Disorder. *American Family Physician*, 94(3), 236-240.
- Rapkin, A. J., & Mikacich, J. A. (2013). Premenstrual syndrome and premenstrual dysphoric disorder in adolescents. *Current Opinion in Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 25(6), 448-456.
- Ryu, A., & Kim, T.-H. (2015). Premenstrual Syndrome: A Mini Review. *Maturitas*, 82(4), 436-440.

Steiner, M., & Yonkers, K. A. (2007). The premenstrual syndrome: Who suffers and how to help. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 353(10), 1-6.

Schneider, T. R., Broderick, J. E., & Junghaenel, D. U. (2011). Personality traits and affective responses to stress. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*, 71(1), 30-34.

Williams, P. G., & Zimmerman, L. M. (2016). Personality and health: The mediating role of health behaviors. *Journal of Personality*, 84(1), 1-16.